

THE THEORETICAL ISSUES OF IMPROVING STATE FUNCTIONS IN
WORKING WITH YOUNG PEOPLE IN OUR COUNTRY

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Annotation: This thesis primarily focuses on the theoretical-legal foundations of state functions in working with young people. Additionally, it explores the principles of existing legislation and provides analysis. The conclusion of the thesis offers recommendations for legislation and practice.

Keywords: youth, state functions, youth organizations, privileges, appeal, decision and law.

Thinking about what benefits society can gain from analyzing, studying, and organizing state functions in working with youth, it is likely that every member of society would find it intriguing. Aligning the activities of youth with the state through intellectual intervention could greatly benefit them. However, the topic in our thesis is quite broad and carries significant legal importance.

It is understood that when analyzing the topic of this thesis, it is necessary to first understand the theoretical-legal aspect of state functions. Scholar Saydullayev Sh.A, in his work, expresses the following thoughts regarding the state function: "Studying issues related to state functions serves to provide a deeper understanding of its content, significance within society, and its deeper societal role. The essence of any state is primarily manifested in its activities and functions. Recognizing the diversity of state activity domains, it is imperative to distinctly categorize its activities." As a result, the nature of the state is embodied, carried out, and evolves in these fundamental directions, also reflecting the state's mode of existence. Thus,

state functions are intrinsically related to its duties and essence, and as the nature of the state evolves, its functions similarly undergo change. Therefore, state functions represent the main (core) directions of state activity aimed at achieving the goals and tasks of the state. [1].

Does the state's work with young people represent its fundamental and responsible function in carrying out state functions, or is it a different function?

According to statistical data [2], there are 1.2 billion young people aged 15 to 24 in the world today, constituting 16 percent of the world's population. The target date for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is 2030, by which time the youth population is expected to increase by 7 percent, reaching nearly 1.3 billion.

Taking this thesis forward, state policy towards youth, the measures and its basis for working with youth are analyzed in the national legal framework. Additionally, the legal foundations of recognizing youth, concepts related to the state function, youth organizations, non-governmental organizations targeting youth, and the analysis of privileges and preferences granted to the youth are scrutinized.

The study employs general legal methods including analysis, specificity, comparison, statistical and generalization methods.

In our country, the following forward trends have been identified and efforts have been made to further reinforce the legal basis of existing mechanisms for state policy towards youth and working with them in order to enhance the orientation of state functions in working with youth from a scientific-theoretical perspective:

-The younger generation has always been at the center of attention for the state because the activity and dynamism of this social group are considered a source for further vibrant development of the country. Given that more than half of Uzbekistan's population constitutes individuals aged between 15 and 30, a revision of current legislation is underway;

-Based on the situation as of January 1, 2022, the population aged 30 and under amounts to 19.6 million individuals, representing 55.6% of the total permanent population. Therefore, as a key trend in modern Uzbekistan, greater attention will be paid to the voice of young people in the process of making various decisions.

-Further enhancement of the position of the youth leader in order to establish new unique mechanisms for working with young people.

-In order to support and empower young people at an institutional level, the Youth Affairs Agency was established on June 30, 2020 [3], leading to the development of a new stage in the state policy towards young people, effective solutions to issues in the field of youth, comprehensive support for them, as well as ensuring effective coordination and alignment of the activities of competent authorities.

As a result of the establishment's initiatives, the position of youth leaders was established from 2022, and they are now actively carrying out their activities in local communities.

In recent years, a series of legislative acts aimed at further enhancing working with young people by the state and the government have been adopted. In particular, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-92 of January 19, 2022, "On measures to further enhance the system of working with youth in local communities," the decree No. PD-96 of January 20, 2022, "On turning the 'Safar' intellectual game into a public educational initiative and measures to develop other intellectual games," the decree of the President's Office No. PD-60 of 2022 "On the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," the decree No. PD-61 of April 26, 2023, "On additional measures to assist and ensure the permanent employment of youth," the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 312 of June 7, 2022, "On further enhancing the system of studying and solving youth issues," the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers 617 of

October 4, 2021, "On additional measures to support socially vulnerable youth," and various other normative-legal documents have been adopted.

Many different scientific, scientific-legal, and public articles, collections, and dissertations (monographs) have been written on various issues related to youth up to the present day. The majority of these cover social, economic, and spiritual-intellectual aspects. For example, among works from Uzbek scholars, there are titles such as Qurbonov R. "The Role of the National Idea in Raising Youth in the Spirit of Patriotic Patriotism. Title of Philosophy" - Tashkent, 2009, 24 pages, Tangriyev L. "Youth Policy Subject: Disability Issue: Political Sciences" - dissertation abstract, Tashkent 2001, 22 pages, Temirova N. "The Dialectics of Shaping the Spiritual Culture of Uzbekistan's Youth with the Universal and National Values" - Tashkent, O'zFA Philosophy and Law Institute, 2009, Tulenova G. "The Role of Spiritual Factors in Enhancing Youth Social Activity (social-philosophical analysis): Doctorate in Philosophy" - dissertation abstract - Tashkent TATU, 2006, 32 pages, Yuldashev M. "Issues of the Formation of the Political Culture of Youth in the Process of Educating Youth in the Independent Republic of Uzbekistan (doctoral dissertation)" - Tashkent O'zMU, 1999, Rasulov R.O. "Pragmatic Foundations of Managing the System of Youth Affairs in New Uzbekistan (social-philosophical analysis)." Doctoral dissertations in the field of philosophy, and from European literature, H. A. Shapiro (ed.), The Cambridge Companion to Archaic Greece. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2007. Pp. xiii, 303; maps 3, figs. 42.; Yelishev S.O. Social manipulation of youth: scientific monograph. - Moscow KANoN+"Rehabilitation" 2019. - 336 p.; Kaygorodov P.V. Social-philosophical analysis of the problem of abandoning the concept of a person as the basis of self-identification: a monograph ... candidate of philosophical sciences. - Tomsk, 2020. - 155 p.; Usmonov S.K. Defensive type of consciousness of young people: a social-philosophical analysis: based on the materials of the Republic of Tajikistan: a monograph ... candidate of philosophical sciences. -

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In scientific-philosophical literature, the concept of "youth" has not been universally defined, leading to a diverse usage of the term. In literature, the definition of "youth" emphasizes "a social-demographic group identified based on a specific age characteristic that distinguishes them from others as an active subject of socialization, involvement in culture, and social development within modern youth boundaries [4].

To date, there is no single scientific definition that universally and functionally aligns with the general system of society for the concept of "youth," nor has its philosophical content and significance been adequately elucidated. The term "youth" typically denotes the life of individuals in their early stages, encompassing childhood, adolescence, and the period of reaching adulthood. Additionally, external characteristics specific to youth, such as agility, ardor, independence, and a creative spirit, are of paramount importance.

In summary, the analysis suggests that revisiting the direction and specific strategies of working with youth in the context of state functions and shaping clear strategies to provide them an appropriate place in both the public and private sectors is crucial.

In 2024, our esteemed President declared the year as "**The Year of Supporting Youth and Entrepreneurship**," signaling the implementation of the "**Uzbekistan 2030**" strategy that will define our future progress. Additionally, for the first time in our history, the amended Constitution was adopted through a nationwide referendum, aimed at elevating the fundamental rights outlined in our Basic Law, thus making it the most important duty of the state to start paying

attention to the youth, their intellectual and spiritual essence, and serve as the main part of state functions with the goal of harnessing these rights.

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